

EVALUATION OF THE CRITERIA FOR CONTRACTOR'S SELECTION IN THE NIGERIAN OIL AND GAS ENGINEERING, PROCUREMENT AND CONSTRUCTION (EPC) PROJECTS

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ABSTRACT

Contractor's selection for projects is an important decision in a project value chain that affects the project cost, time and quality. This study aims to evaluate the criteria for contractor's selection in the Nigerian oil and gas Engineering, Procurement and Construction (EPC) projects. The study is timely due to the dearth of studies on this subject in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria. The study uses a multi-case study survey design. The study samples all the 113 EPC professionals including Architects, Engineers, Procurement Officers and Quantity Surveyors affiliated to selected oil and gas corporations in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria. A total of 81 questionnaires were returned representing a 71.68 percent return rate. The study finds that guarantee management, banking arrangement and bond, and risk management are the most important criteria for contractor selection. However, factor analysis estimates indicate that twenty seven (27) contractor's selection criteria can be broadly grouped into two major factors of technical and managerial competencies. The study thus concludes that EPC contractor's selection criteria are broadly categorised into technical and managerial competencies. The study therefore recommends that clienteles of the oil and gas EPC projects should make adequate assessment of all aspects of managerial and technical competencies of contractors during the process of contractor's selection to ensure superior EPC project performance.

Keywords: Contractors, Engineering Procurement Construction, Oil and Gas, Selection Criteria

Practical Applications

The study evaluated the criteria for contractor's selection in the Nigerian oil and gas Engineering, Procurement and Construction (EPC) projects. This study fills the gap on the dearth of studies on oil and gas EPC contracts and procurement. The most important criteria for EPC contractor's to include Guarantee Management, Banking Arrangement & bond, Risk management, Technical Evaluation and Insurance. The findings of this study will equip government and individual clients who want to embark on oil and gas projects with the essentials to look out for in the selection of contracting entities. The adoption of a multiple criteria decision approach with an elaborate managerial and technical criteria for the selection of EPC contractors will be fundamental in the Nigerian oil and gas industry.

INTRODUCTION

The oil and gas as well as the construction industry make fundamental contributions to the socio-economic development. The construction sector is an important sector of the economy that provides superior infrastructure services to all sectors including the oil and gas industry. The contribution of the construction sector will not materialise with project failure due to the selection of inappropriate contractors (Elsayah, 2016; Fard et al., 2015). Thus the growing interest in contractor selection procedure may not be unrelated to the share size of project in the economy and the far reaching effect of the choice of contractor on project success (Liefers, 2012). A growing body of literature finds strong relationships between project performance and contractor selection. This is because contractors are the primary drivers of project objectives and successes. Thus the selection of appropriate contractor is one of the most important processes that influence project performance. The prequalification and the subsequent selection of appropriate construction contractor are critical steps and decisions in a project value chain. Thus a growing interest in the management of EPC projects and the growing importance of contractor's selection process in project delivery. The procedure for the selection of contractor involves the use of important criteria and methodology to determine the choice of qualified contractor to handle a project. The choice of the efficient or effective criteria is thus very important for the decision making (Hatush, 1996; Huang, 2011; Jafari, 2013; Puri & Tiwari, 2014; Rashvand et al., 2015; Ruqaishi & Bashir, 2015; Elsayah, 2016; Rashid et al., 2017; Araujo et al., 2018;).

Contractor selection is a dynamic and challenging exercise that encompasses many conflicting interests. The selection of contractor is very fundamental for project effectiveness and efficiency. Wrongful process may lead to poor or less than optimal outcome that may jeopardise the client's objectives. The increasing deployment of project management towards achieving business strategy underscores the importance of contractor selection process. Many multinationals now dedicate a unit or department to handle project management and procurement. In order to achieve project strategy, contractor's selection may be based on – lowest cost, qualification, cost and quality, sole source and fixed budget (Roseke, 2019). In a bid to remain competitive construction clients must engage efficient and effective contractors to guaranty value for money (Lee, 2016). However, choosing appropriate contracting may not be that easy as it may appears (Idrus et al., 2011).

Risk management is fundamental in contractor selection process. Outsourcing services through contractors selection offers numerous benefits such as cuts in overheads and running costs, improved efficiency and risks reduction among others. Wrongful process may increase project risk factors. Inefficient process may have significant repercussions on the project performance. Effective contractor's selection is very beneficial to public institutions which imply the importance of contractor selection process in project development. For many jurisdictions the lowest bidder post prequalification is the preferred procurement method for contractors. However, this leads to the tendency for the best bid from the best contractors to loose out. Thus the use of lowest bid criterion in public procurement throws up lot of difficulties which may result in inefficiencies in project performance. This invariably implies that construction in developing economies continues to encounter significant challenges including poor project performance due to many problems including the qualification of contractors, lowest bid selection criterion and weak resources (Alptekin & Alptekin, 2017; Banaitiene & Banaitis, 2006; Dave et al., 2017; Maqsoom et al., 2019; Mousakhani et al., 2018).

The most efficient public procurement system for contractor selection in Taiwan is the committee ranking system. However the committee system has a demerit of personal and

subjective preferences of individual committee members (Cheng et al., 2020). In the Netherlands, the most popular procedures are public and restricted (tendering with prequalification). Additionally, the methods of contract are the lowest price criterion and the multiple criteria selection (MCS) or best value. The lowest bid criterion has been linked to many project challenges thus the growing use of the MCS (Liefers, 2012). Thus in order to improve project performance there is the need for the evaluation of contractors on multiple criteria before contract award. This sets the background for the optimal performance of project built on the selection of competent contractor (Hatush, 1996). The construction industry has tended to show favouritism in the selection of main contractor which normally affect the selection of subcontractors and suppliers. This continues to be a major challenge for construction project delivery (Ajayi et al., 2010).

The management of energy has become fundamental in the strategy of most countries due to its fundamental economic importance. Similarly, the oil and gas sector as one of the largest sub sectors of the energy value chain is assuming increasing sophistication and specialisation. Thus countries continue to improve in the management and contractual arrangement for the production, extraction and the processing in the oil and gas sector. A low risk approach to project implementation in the energy sector is the engineering, procurement and construction (EPC) contracts (Niayeshnia et al., 2020). Oil and gas projects share significant similarities with construction projects (Roshidi et al., 2021; Salama et al., 2008). However, the overwhelming challenges of the oil and gas sector have been the driving force behind innovations in the industry. Thus the procurement in oil and gas sector is more dynamic and sophisticated than construction and other sectors. Consequently the sector has developed a whole lot of innovative procurement strategies to match its environment (Mohammad & Price, 2004). Resources rich countries around the world are deepening transformation of the oil and gas sector in order to improve on efficiency and effectiveness as a sure path to industrialisation, full employment and long run growth (Olawuyi, 2017). The phenomenal growth in the global economy and the corresponding expansion in the oil and gas production all over the world have positioned the sector as one of the largest and most dynamic industry (Aldhaheri et al. 2018). There is a corresponding challenges and sophistication in oil and gas construction system as the world economy continues to yawn for oil and gas product and services (Berends, 2007).

Nigeria is an emerging economy in the global energy system as a leading member of the Organisation of Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC). However, the Nigerian oil and gas sector is relatively underdeveloped and lack commensurate contributions to the economy (Rui et al., 2018). It is of utmost importance that all aspects of the oil and gas sector especially EPC projects procurement need to at optimal level of effectiveness and efficiency to be able to make superior contributions to the emerging economy of Nigeria. EPC in oil and gas are under researched in Nigeria, which puts the investors and regulators in darkness over investment risks (Ogbu & Ehigiator-Irughe, 2020). The dearth of studies on oil and gas EPC contracts and procurement in recent time provides a background for this study. This paper aims to investigate the criteria for contractor selection in EPC contracts in the oil and gas sector. The paper is divided into introduction, literature, methodology, result and discussion as well as conclusion and recommendation.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A growing body of knowledge addresses aspects of EPC projects procurement in the oil and gas sector and related subjects (Mohammad & Price, 2003; Olawuyi, 2017; Rui et al., 2018; Ogbu & Ehigiator-Irughe, 2020). Hatush, (1996) adopts survey design to interview construction professional on the construction bidding process including prequalification procedure and bid evaluation as well as the criteria for contractor selection. The study investigates the relationships between contractor selection criteria and project success factors. The study presents a framework or model for contractor selection which combines project goals and contractor's data. In addition the study formulates strategy for evaluation that combines client goals (ends) and contractor data (means) base on multi-attribute theory for the ranking of contractors. Mohammad and Price (2003) reviewed the practices of procurement in the Malaysian oil and gas sector from the 1970s to date as a background for further studies on the subject. Similarly, Mohammad and Price (2004) investigated the current practices of procurement in the oil and gas sector in order to develop improve oil procurement strategy and management in the sector. Tarawneh (2004) assessed the perception of clients on contractors' prequalification criteria using Jordanian construction industry as a case study. The study adopted interviews of top level managers of major construction clients in Jordan. The study finds divergent views between public and private clients on prequalification criteria. Public clients tend to favour lowest price post prequalification, whereas private client favour contractor's effectiveness to work with the client as a team. The paper concludes that Jordanian construction needs special prequalification criteria to satisfy good manufacturing practices.

Salama et al. (2006) investigated the criteria for bid evaluation in the selection of contractors in the Egyptian construction industry. The study involves a survey of 100 project managers on bid evaluation criteria. The study finds that the main criteria for contractor prequalification are experience, resources and financial status. The main criteria for contractor technical evaluation include quality control, technical supervision and technology. The main criteria for contractor financial evaluation include bid price, fair estimate and schedule payment. And finally, the method use for final evaluation includes lowest bid price, closest value to pre-estimated cost and lowest bid price after dividing with criteria score. The study recommends for the development of code of practice and the improvement of the current project procurement practices. Banaitiene and Banaitis (2006) investigated the criteria for assessment for the selection of construction contractors in Lithuania and other countries and analyses data relevant to contractor's qualification. Given that most systems have tended to use lowest bid price which have proven in most cases not to be efficient because of its lack of commitment for duration and quality of construction project. A better approach of the client is to add other criteria for a robust process that produces the most qualified, efficient and reliable contractors to achieve expected outcome in projects. Thus the bid criteria must include quantitative and qualitative variables and should be compared. The paper makes suggestions based on expert opinion on improving construction contractor's selection criteria. Hatush and Skitmore (2006) examine the criteria for the selection of contractors by construction clients in the UK. The paper uses extensive interviews with public and private project clienteles. The paper makes suggestions for the improvement of the current practices. Thuyet et al. (2007) investigated the risk factors that affect oil and gas EPC projects in Vietnam and plausible mitigation measures against the identified risks. The study deployed questionnaire survey and interviews with project managers and executives of petro Vietnam. The study finds the risk factors to include bureaucracy, project approval procedures, weak design, weak project team, poor tendering practices, and slow internal approval procedure. Furthermore, the study identifies plausible mitigating measures to include public service reform, partnership with foreign organisations, project management training, using multiple criteria decision making technique for contractor's selection and

increasing the power of project team. The study recommends for the implementation of the mitigating measures in EPC projects procurement for better project performance. Salama et al. (2008) investigated the causes of project delays in the oil and gas EPC project in UAE. The study deploys interviews of experts and questionnaire survey of a sample of 100 construction practitioners on factors responsible for delays. The study finds that the most important causes of delays are delay in purchase of long lead items, delays in deliveries, inadequate contractor's experience and knowledge of technical staff, poor project management and shortage of qualified engineers. Additionally, the study finds a significant correlation between delays within Front End Engineering Design (FEED) and the total project delays. The study suggests for corrective measures on delays during the procurement stage of oil and gas EPC projects.

Ajayi et al. (2010) investigated the criteria for the prequalification, tender assessment and selection of subcontractors and suppliers in building construction projects towards a successful project delivery. The study adopted survey design using a sample of construction professionals in the building industry. Some sixty (60) questionnaires were administered through random sampling but only forty two (42) were returned completely filled ready for analysis. The study finds that construction plant is the most important criterion for subcontractors in the pre-qualification stage whereas equipment and information technology are the major criteria for supplier selection. Huang, (2011) reviews the models for contractor's selection as well as practical criteria for contractor's selection. Some of these models are the cost consideration framework, TOPSIS (technique for order preference by similarity to ideals solution) and SAW-G (Simple Additive Weighting with Grey relations), prequalification method, the construction management at risk method and the multi-criteria evaluation models. Some of the practical approaches are financial competence, technical competition, managerial competence, quality, safety and senior manager, and current projects/backlog. The paper concludes that some may select contractor based on contractor's experience, reliability, competence and safety record and programme and contractor's capability and capacity. Idrus et al. (2011) examine the criteria for selecting contractors in the Malaysian construction sector. The contractor's selection criteria were ranked by a sample of 150 construction professionals. The study deploys frequency and severity index to analyse the data. The study finds that the most important criteria for contractor's selection are track performance, financial capacity and technical capacity. Liefers, (2012) investigated public procurement in the Netherlands. The study adopts the use of three case studies with interviews of the managers as well as document scrutiny. The study concludes that traditional projects that are straight forward may use the method of lowest price criterion while more innovative and technical projects may use the method of MCS. Jafari, (2013) studies construction contractor prequalification and develops a model of prequalification that deploys quality function deployment(QFD) that take into cognisance the project objectives, clients requirements and expectations and the contractor's abilities.

Puri and Tiwari, (2014) examine construction contractor's selection process both in theory and practices. The study adopts survey design to sample project managers in India. The study finds clients preference for experience, reliability, competence and safety. The study concludes that detail contractor's evaluation before the selection significantly contributes to project success. Fard et al. (2015) undertake a survey of contractor's selection criteria and present a model for contractor selection and methodology for managerial decision criteria. The study uses non parametric statistics for data analysis. The study recommends the use expert judgement and non parametric statistics in the determination of the most efficient criteria relating to cost, time, safety and quality. Rashvand et al. (2015) attempt to develop a robust model of contractor selection based on contractor's management capability and practices. The study deploys a system of detail study of critical contractor's management performance factors, analytical network project (ANP) model, and ultimately model field validation. The resulting model

enhances client prequalification decision making and also helps to improve contractor's management practices. Ruqaishi and Bashir (2015) examine the causes of projects' delay in the Omani's oil and gas industry. The study uses questionnaire survey of 59 project managers. The study deploys nonparametric statistics of reliability test, Kruskal Wallis and median for data analysis. The study finds seven causes of project delay including six general causes across all industries such as inadequate site management and supervision by contractors; weak subcontractors; poor planning and scheduling of projects; inadequate management of contract schedule; material delay; and poor communication among stakeholders. The seventh cause i.e. inadequate interaction with suppliers in the engineering and procurement stages is unique to oil and gas EPC projects. To avoid unnecessary delays in EPC projects it is important that these findings are integrated into the criteria of contractor selection for EPC projects.

Elsayah (2016) investigates the practices and procedure of contractor's selection in the Libyan Construction Industry (LCI) with the aim of developing a framework for an efficient contractor's selection model. The study deploys two case studies with questionnaire survey. The population for the study includes clienteles, contractors, consultants and construction professionals. Descriptive statistics, t-test and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) Model were used for data analysis. The study uses a combination of AHP (Analytic Hierarchy Process) and TOPSIS (Technique for Order Performance by Similarity to Ideal Solution) models to evaluate the contractor's selection practices. The study deploys Delphi technique to develop a framework for contractor's selection. The study finds that the LCI lacks a framework for contractor selection. Consequently, the study develops a comprehensive framework for contractor selection process (CSP) for the LCI. Lee, (2016) examines the practices of contractor's selection by Malaysian housing developers. The study develops three research questions and seven hypotheses. The study uses a postal survey of 545 members of Malaysian Real Estate and Housing Development Association (REHDA) for the year 2009/2010. A total of 155 questionnaires were returned from 64 small firms, 38 medium firms and 53 large firms. This translates to a response rate of 24.4 percent. The study analyse the data using Partial Least Square –Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM). The findings were crossed validated by expert group. The study finds that price and relationships have little impact on contractor selection. Furthermore, contractor's ranking in finance, past experience and corporate expertise play significant role in contractor's selection.

Olatunji et al. (2016) review the Nigerian public procurement act 2007 and proffers plausible amendments. The study identifies a number of loopholes in the 2007 Act to include –no clear cut qualification for procurement managers, no definition of the forms of procurement, non inclusion of Architect Engineering and Construction (AEC) professionals on the procurement council, preference for lowest bidder, only two methods of tendering, only competitive bidding and no provision for dispute management. The study thus recommends for the amendments the 2007 act to free procurement from politicians; the inclusion of AECs in the procurement council; and the adoption of best value bid approach. Wee et al. (2016) examine the impact of skill competence of contractors on project delay. The study samples a total 51 G7 contractors. The study finds that managerial skills, financial skills and human resources management skills are important competencies for contractors. Alptekin and Alptekin (2017) examine other criteria beside lowest bidders that could be used in contractors' selection for better efficiency. The study uses a survey of public administrators at the Eskisehir Osmangazi University and deploys TOPSIS (Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to the Ideal Solution) for the analysis. The study finds that termination of previous contract is the most important criterion out of 12 criteria. Dave et al. (2017) examine the criteria for contractors' selection and make suggestions for the improvement to the bidding and selection process. Nkanta et al. (2017) investigate contractor's pre-qualification criteria and their determinants in the Niger Delta

region of Nigeria with a view to improving contractor's selection in a recessed economy. The study deploys random sampling to survey a total of 75 consulting firms and 26 public institutions in Niger Delta States, Nigeria. The study uses descriptive statistics and factor analysis for the data analysis. The study finds that the most important prequalification criteria to be contractor's past performance, contractor's experience and evidence of incorporation. The factor analysis estimates indicates that 75 criteria were reduced to seven components including contractor's resources, incentive factor, project risks factor, performance factors, procurement factors, managerial factors and technical factors. The paper recommends for emphasise on human resources and previous records in contractor's selection.

Olawuyi, (2017) reviews the evolution of local content requirement and procurement laws in the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) region. Additionally, the paper makes a comparative analysis of the oil and gas law of MENA countries to identify some important advantages and risks. The paper recommends on improving frameworks that accelerate both the local content requirement (LCR) and foreign investment. Rashid et al. (2017) examine contractors' selection criteria in bid evaluation process. The study finds through a wide array of sources including literature review and content analysis of various materials at least 43 criteria broadly divided into seven broad criteria including management capability, financial competence, experience, resources, technical competence, health, safety and environment (HSE), and risk management. The study recommends a number of multiple criteria decision methods for contractor's selection including Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP), the Preference Ranking Organisation Method for Enrichment of Evaluation (PROMETHEE), the Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS) and the Multi-Attribute Utility Theory (MAUT). Zabair and Atugba (2017) examine the impact of contractor's technical competence on cost and time performance of public projects in north central Nigeria. The study is based on a survey of 225 contractors, consultants and clients. 177 questionnaires representing 78.67 percent returned rate were returned ready for analysis. The study finds that contractor's technical competence significantly affects project cost performance but not significant on project time performance. The study concludes that specific contractor's technical competence may be used as prequalification criteria in public projects development.

Mousakhani et al. (2018) investigate the factors affecting contractors' selection in order to formulate an efficient process for evaluation and selection of contractors. The paper first identifies the important risk factors in contractor selection and then selected the most important risk factor. Subsequently, the paper uses expert opinion to determine the most important factors in contractor selection. Ultimately, the paper examines the relationships between these factors and contractors risk management. Aldhaheeri et al. (2018) examine the factors affecting the effectiveness of EPC projects in satisfying stated objectives in the perspective of the end users. The study adopts a survey design using online questionnaire for 275 end users and 213 responses were returned. The study finds that project objectives and end user engagement factors positively influences the effectiveness of EPCs. Additionally, end users show more preference to quality than time and cost in project success triangle. Furthermore, engaging end users in project early stages reduces the possibility of design modification and improve project cost and time performance and end user's satisfaction. Valitova et al. (2018) investigate risks and their mitigation in construction project development based on the viewpoint of management. The study emphasises on risks related to the selection of unqualified contractor. The methodology of contractors' risk assessment reveals that apart from factors related to project cost, it is important to also use criteria such as qualification, reputation, material and technical competence, and previous work performance. The study presents a universal methodology that satisfies all stakeholders based on known information about companies.

Araujo et al. (2018) review recent literature review on contractor selection criteria published between 1993 through 2015. The paper clusters the criteria into twenty three subgroups under eight (8) subsectors of the construction system. Rui et al. (2018) examine Nigerian oil and gas projects using some 65 projects. The study finds that oil and gas projects in Nigeria on the average have high rate of cost overruns of 38percent (with a std.dev. of 39%) and time overruns of 37percent(with a std.dev. of 41%), a fatality rate of 0.027 and oil spillage rate of 18.51. Thus the performance of oil and gas projects in Nigeria is about the worst in the world. The Nigerian oil and gas projects are of low technological challenges which imply that technology challenges are not the underlying causes of underperformance. The study reveals that other issues such as local content, community, security and partnership are very important. The study recommends a system of practices based on risk assessment at the engineering and procurement stages to eliminate project risks in future oil and gas project development. Kamaruddeen et al. (2019) examine construction contractors' selection criteria in Serawak, Malaysia. The study uses survey research design and a sampling of 336 contractors, developers and quantity surveying firms using a questionnaire. Only 71 of questionnaires were returned for analysis representing a 21.13percent. The study uses mean and relative importance index to analyse the data. The study finds that contractors' management, technical and financial capacities are the most important contractors' selection criteria. Maqsoom et al. (2019) investigates the bid evaluation process and criteria for consultants and clients in Pakistan. The paper uses the relative important index and severity index for data analysis. The paper finds that planning, credit worthiness, transitional plans, technical, financial capability, previous performance and quality to be the most important factors for contractor's selection. Furthermore, contractors are more likely to be successful if multi-criteria are used for their selection. Cheng et al. (2020) develop a Bayesian fuzzy model for committee decision to optimally select the most efficient construction contractor for public projects.

Niayeshnia et al. (2020) examine EPC projects in terms of analysis, prioritisation, ranking, and efficiency in the energy industry of Iran under the TOPSIS multi-criteria group decision making methodology. The paper finds that the most important influencing factor on project is engineering (technical); and that construction has superior influence on productivity than procurement. Furthermore, the paper indicates along with TOPSIS analysis that inadequate planning and scheduling, design, and layout; poor project planning and control; and inefficient product performance are the most important factors in EPC project failure in the energy industry of Iran. Ogbu and Ehigiator-Irughe (2020) use qualitative approach to investigate cost overruns in depot construction project, in Lagos state, Nigeria. The study finds that most cost items experienced overruns with a cumulative cost overrun of 106percent. Most of the overruns are design and construction related. The study recommends for the early engagement of consultants in oil and gas EPC construction projects and the adoption of standard conditions of contract instead of customised conditions. Arena et al. (2022) examine how firm level data could be used to formulate local content (LC) target by international oil companies in oil producing countries. The paper uses data from the World Bank Enterprises Survey (ES) Unit to show how firm level data could be used for policy making. The paper indicates that firm level data provide superior estimate of the capability of domestic firms to supply inputs to the oil industry, whereas sector level data over estimates the local content. The study concludes that firm level data could be deployed as the basis for more precise design of local content policies in oil producing countries and that enterprises survey may be the model for data collection for policy actions. Ravari et al. (2020) develop a model of contractor's selection using linear and exponential model using the Particle Swarm Optimisation (PSO) algorithm technique. The model is based on contractor's technical capability, contractor's behavioural capability, client's capacity and facility, and project outsourcing goals. The study finds that linear function provides superior model for efficient contractor selection. Roshidi et al., (2021) investigate cost overruns in

fabrication onshore oil and gas projects in Malaysia. The study suggests the establishment of effective planning, monitoring and control (management) at the procurement stage to improve cost management of resource allocation in onshore oil and gas fabrication projects.

METHODOLOGY

In this section the research design, sampling, method of data collection and analytical strategy for this study is discussed.

Research Design is the glue or plan or strategy that connects the entire research processes and procedures which includes research questions, hypothesis, sampling, data collection, and data analysis (Lavrakas, 2008). The study adopts the multiple case survey design approach. This involves the selection of some International Oil Corporation (IOCs) and national oil and gas corporations to understudy their approaches to EPC contract management through questionnaire survey. The national oil and gas corporations selected for this study includes Warri Refinery and Petrochemical Corporation (WRPC) and Port Harcourt Refinery Corporation (PHRC). The IOCs selected for this study includes Chevron, Mobil & Shell.

Sampling is the procedure for drawing a subset of the population for a study (Collis & Hussey, 2009). The target population for this study includes all officers involve in the management EPC projects in the selected corporations. These officers include procurement officers, project engineers, architects and quantity surveyors. The study adopts census sampling to reach all possible respondents. The total number of respondents is Architects (17), Quantity Surveyors (23), Engineers (38) and Procurement Officers (35) which sums up to one hundred and thirteen (113) across the five selected oil and gas corporations. The data for this study were collected through the administration of a structured questionnaire. The questionnaires were based on seventeen criteria and each rated on a five point Likert scale (1 to 5).

The study employed both descriptive and inferential statistics to analyse the data. The descriptive statistics includes frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation. The inferential statistics includes Kruskal Wallis H test and Factor Analysis.

Descriptive Statistics includes the summary of analysis and presentation of a data set including measures of central tendency (mean, median & mode) and measure of variability (including range, quartile, dispersion, variance & standard deviation.) and frequency distribution (CFI, 2021).

Factor Analysis was used to reduce a large set of variable to smaller number of factors that captures the correlation and variability among the original variables. There are a number of approaches to factor analysis including principal component analysis (PCA), common factor analysis, image factoring, and maximum likelihood method. (statistics solutions, 2022).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Descriptive Statistics: The result of the study or field work and corresponding discussion are presented in this section. The professionals in the case studies are about 113. All the 113 professionals were sampled but only 81 of professionals returned the questionnaires filled and ready for analysis. This represents 71 percent response rate. The highest proportional response

rate was from architects (88.25%), while the lowest response rate was from the engineers (63.15%) (See table 1).

Table 1: Response Rate

Professional	Questionnaires Distributed	Questionnaires Retrieved	Response Rate
Architecture	17	15	88.25
Engineer	38	24	63.15
Procurement Officer	35	25	71.42
Quantity Surveyor	23	17	73.91
Total	113	81	71.68

The proportional response of the professionals indicates that the highest response is from procurement officers with a total of 25 representing 30.9 percent of the total response. The lowest response is from Architects with a total of 15 representing 18.5percent. The data indicates that the highest academic qualification of most of the respondents is B.Sc/B.Tech (61.7%) while the least proportion of the professional hold a PhD as highest academic qualification (16%). Additionally, the respondents were distributed within the oil firms almost equally with the IOCs (i.e. Chevron, Mobil & Shell) having 18 respondents each, while PHRC and WRPC have 14 and 13 respondents respectively. Furthermore, in terms of cognate experience the largest sub group among the respondents is 6to 11years (42.0%) and the least subgroups are 0to5years and over20years (4% each). Finally, in terms of number of projects handled by the professionals, the largest subgroups is the category with above 20 projects (37%) and lowest category is the subgroup with less than 5 projects (1.2%) (see table 2).

Table 2: Background of Respondents

	Profession of respondents	Frequency	Percentage
1	Procurement officers	25	30.9
2	Engineers	24	29.6
3	Quantity surveyor	17	21.0
4	Architects	15	18.5
	Total	81	100
	Highest academic qualification		
1	M.Sc./M.Tech.	50	61.7
2	BSc./B.Tech.	18	22.2
3	PhD.	13	16.0
	Total	81	100
	Affiliation of respondents		
1	Chevron	18	22.2
2	Mobil	18	22.2
3	Shell	18	22.2
4	PHRC	14	17.3
5	WRPC	13	16
	Total	81	100
	Years of cognate experience		
1	11-15years	34	42.0
2	6-10years	21	25.9
3	16-20years	18	22.2
4	0-5years	4	4.9
5	Over 20years	4	4.9
	Total	81	100
	Number of projects		

1	Above 20	30	37
2	16-20	28	34.6
3	11-15	12	14.8
4	5-10	10	12.3
5	Less than 5	1	1.2
	Total	81	100

Mean Rank: The data from the fieldwork indicates that out of the 27 criteria for contractor's selection Guarantee management, Banking arrangement & bond, Risk management, Technical Evaluation and Insurance are the highest ranked with a respective mean rank of 4.9630, 4.9506, 4.9383, 4.9383 and 4.8642. The least ranked criteria includes Financial status, Goodwill between contractor & Client, Selection of sub-contractors, Organisation culture and Contiguity with a respective mean of 4.4321, 4.2346, 4.2222, 4.1481 and 3.6173.

Kruskal Wallis (KW) rank: the estimates of the Kruskal Wallis Test indicate that the respondents strongest agreement on the criteria of contractor's selection across the five oil and gas firms are Finance stability, Corporate reputation, Quality assurance, Return analysis and Banking arrangement & bond with the respective p-value of .986, .847, .847, .784, and .530. However, the respondents disagreed most on the following criteria Insurance, Goodwill between contractor & Client, Performance of the with the respective p-value less than 0.005.

Table 3: Contractor Selection Criteria -Mean Rank And Kruskal Wallis (KW) Rank

Criteria for Contractor Selection	Mean	Std deviation	Mean Rank	Chi-Square	P-value
Insurance	4.86	0.54	5	18.542	.001
Goodwill between contractor & Client	4.23	0.98	24	15.748	.003
Performance of the contractor	4.80	0.45	11	14.755	.005
Contiguity	3.61	0.88	27	14.401	.006
Management by objective	4.45	0.59	21	10.596	.031
Logistics management	4.57	0.86	18	9.825	.043
Organisation culture	4.14	0.65	26	8.282	.082
Credit rating	4.63	0.60	16	8.053	.090
Safety critical consideration	4.83	0.54	8	7.853	.097
Selection of sub-contractors	4.22	0.98	25	7.838	.098
Physical inspection by client	4.56	0.59	20	6.804	.147
Knowledgeability/familiarities	4.84	0.48	7	6.649	.156
Readiness of the contractor	4.73	0.65	13	6.596	.159
Competitive pricing	4.71	0.55	15	5.931	.204
Contractor's managerial capability	4.83	0.56	9	5.481	.241
Financial status	4.43	0.86	23	5.306	.257
Risk Management	4.94	0.32	3	5.081	.279
Relationship management	4.57	0.72	19	5.018	.285
Technical Evaluation	4.94	0.36	4	4.692	.320
Corporate competence	4.73	0.70	14	4.418	.352
Guarantee management	4.96	0.33	1	3.521	.478
Contractor's business directory	4.43	0.77	22	3.381	.496
Banking arrangement & bond	4.95	0.35	2	3.167	.530
Return analysis	4.80	0.51	12	1.738	.784
Quality assurance	4.81	0.52	10	1.386	.847
Corporate reputation	4.59	0.78	17	1.386	.847
Finance stability	4.85	0.47	6	0.348	.986

Factor Analysis Estimate: the KMO measure of sampling adequacy of 0.792 indicates that the sample is somewhat adequate for factor analysis. Additionally, the Bartlett's test of

sphericity of Approx. Chi-square= 2661.000 with a P-value =0.000 also supports the KMO estimates that the factor analysis can progress or that the sample is adequate for factor analysis.

Table 4: KMO and Bartlett's Test For Sphericity

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of sampling adequacy				0.792
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity			Approx. Chi-Square	2661.000
			Df	351
			p-value	0.000

Variance: the factor analysis was run for 27 contractor's selection criteria to reduce them to two groups. The estimate of the total variance explained indicate six factors with initial Eigen value greater than one (1) i.e.11.104(component 1) to1.217(component 6) which explain between 41.126and 4.507 percent of the variance in the sample respectively. The two components extracted are the components one (1) and two(2) with a respective total extracted sum of square loading of 11.104 and 3.161 and a corresponding percentage of variance of 41.126 and 11.708 respectively. The rotated sums of squared loadings for the two components are 7.378 and 7.883 respectively.

Table 5: Total Variance Explained

Components	Initial Eigenvalue			Extraction Loading			Rotated sums of Squared Loadings Total
	Total	% of variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of variance	Cumulative %	
1	11.104	41.126	41.126	11.104	41.126	41.126	7.883
2	3.161	11.708	52.834	3.161	11.708	52.834	7.378
3	2.548	9.437	62.272				
4	2.193	8.122	70.393				
5	1.412	5.231	75.625				
6	1.217	4.507	80.132				
7	0.821	3.04	83.172				
8	0.768	2.844	86.016				
9	0.633	2.346	88.362				
10	0.6	2.222	90.584				
11	0.46	1.704	92.288				
12	0.386	1.429	93.717				
13	0.337	1.249	94.965				
14	0.262	0.971	95.936				
15	0.241	0.894	96.83				
16	0.193	0.713	97.543				
17	0.139	0.515	98.058				
18	0.134	0.497	98.555				
19	0.103	0.383	98.939				
20	0.076	0.281	99.219				
21	0.06	0.222	99.441				
22	0.044	0.164	99.605				
23	0.037	0.136	99.741				
24	0.031	0.115	99.856				
25	0.022	0.08	99.936				
26	0.013	0.046	99.982				
27	0.005	0.018	100				

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Component Matrix: the estimate of the rotated component matrix indicates that nineteen(19) of the 27 contractor’s selection criteria loaded on component one (F1) and eight(8) out of the total 27 contractor’s selection criteria loaded on component two (F2). The components are appropriately named technical competence (F1) and managerial competence (F2).

Table 6: Rotated Component Matrix

S/N	Factors	Component	
		F1	F2
1	Technical Competence		
1	Safety critical consideration	0.818	
2	Knowledgeability/familiarities	0.778	
3	Guarantee management	0.764	
4	Banking arrangement & bond	0.745	
5	Quality assurance	0.735	
6	Insurance	0.731	
7	Corporate Reputation	0.724	
8	Physical inspection by client	0.701	
9	Corporate competence	0.695	
10	Performance of the contractor	0.686	
11	Selection of sub-contractors	0.674	
12	Competitive pricing	0.664	
13	Finance stability	0.609	
14	Technical evaluation	0.580	
15	Readiness of the contractor	0.570	
16	Organisation culture	0.562	
17	Financial status	0.562	
18	Credit rating	0.551	
19	Return analysis	0.528	
2	Managerial competence		
1	Contractor’s managerial capability		0.828
2	Risk management		0.743
3	Contiguity		0.715
4	Contractor’s business directory		0.682
5	Logistics management		0.628
6	Management by objective		0.601
7	Relationship management		0.598
8	Goodwill between contractor & Client		0.502

Discussion of Result

Mean Ranking: The study finds that the most important criteria for EPC contractor’s to include Guarantee Management, Banking Arrangement & bond, Risk management, Technical Evaluation and Insurance. Several studies have reported similar result (Huang, 2011; Elsayah, 2016; Mousakhani et al., 2018; Maqsoom et al., 2019; Kamaruddeen et al., 2019; Ravari et al., 2020).

The contractor’s selection criteria based on Kruskal Wallis test result indicates that finance stability, corporate reputation, quality assurance, return analysis and banking arrangement & bond are the most important. This finding agrees with a strand of literature (Elsayah, 2016; Wee et al., 2016; Nkanta et al., 2017; Kamaruddeen et al., 2019; Mousakhani et al., 2018; Maqsoom et al., 2019).

A growing number of studies reports finding that technical and managerial competences are the broad fundamental criteria for the selection of oil and gas EPC projects 'contractors (Salama et

al., 2006; Ajayi et al. 2010; Huang, 2011; Idrus et al., 2011; Liefers, 2012; Puri & Tiwari, 2014; Rashvand et al., 2015; Elsayah, 2016; Nkanta et al., 2017; Rashid et al., 2017; Zabair & Atugba, 2017; Adenaiya & Eguh, 2019; Araujo et al., 2018; Mousakhani et al., 2018; Valitova et al., 2018; Kamaruddeen et al., 2019; Maqsoom et al., 2019; Cheng et al., 2020; Niayeshnia et al., 2020; Ravari et al. 2020). Salama et al. (2006) find that in Egypt, technical and financial evaluations are critical post prequalification stages of project procurement before final evaluation. Wee et al. (2016) examine the impact of skill competence of contractors on project delay. The study samples a total 51 G7 contractors. The study finds that managerial skills, financial skills and human resources management skills are important competencies for contractors.

Nkanta et al., (2017) reduce 75 criteria to seven components including contractor's resources, incentive factor, project risks factor, performance factors, procurement factors, managerial factors and technical factors. Rashid et al. (2017) broadly divides selection criteria into seven including management capability, financial competence, experience, resources, technical competence, health, safety and environment (HSE), and risk management. Zabair and Atugba (2017) find that contractor's technical competence significantly affects project cost performance but not significant on project time performance. The study concludes that specific contractor's technical competence may be used as prequalification criteria in public projects in the north central Nigeria. Kamaruddeen et al. (2019) finds that contractors' management, technical and financial capacities are the most important contractors' selection criteria. Maqsoom et al. (2019) finds that planning, credit worthiness, transitional plans, plant/equipment, financial capability, previous performance and quality to be the most important factors for contractor's selection. Niayeshnia et al. (2020) finds that the most important influencing factor on project is engineering; and that construction has superior influence on productivity than procurement. Furthermore, inadequate planning and scheduling, design, and layout; poor project planning and control; and inefficient product performance are the most important factors in EPC project failure in the energy industry of Iran. Finally, Hatush, (1996), Liefer (2012), Rashid et al. (2017) and Maqsoom et al (2019) suggest the adoption of multiple criteria decision methods or multiple criteria selection (MCS) approach in contractor's selection.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The study involves investigation into contractor selection criteria in oil and gas EPC projects in the Nigerian oil and gas industry. The study uses five case studies of 3 IOCs and 2 NOCs. The study deploys census sampling to reach all the targeted 113 Architects, Engineers, Procurement Officers and Quantity Surveyors that are affiliated to these firms. The study finds that the most important criteria for EPC contractors are Guarantee Management, Banking Arrangement & bond, Risk management, Technical Evaluation and Insurance. Further test revealed that the most important contractor's selection criteria are finance stability, corporate reputation, quality assurance, return analysis and banking arrangement & bond. Furthermore, the result indicates that the criteria for EPC projects contractor's selection can be broadly subdivided into two groups of Managerial and technical competences. The study therefore concludes that contractor's selection criteria for oil and gas EPC projects may be broadly grouped into technical and managerial competences. The study therefore recommends for the adoption of a multiple criteria decision approach with an elaborate managerial and technical criteria for the selection of EPC contractors in the Nigerian oil and gas industry.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENTS

Some or all data, models, or code that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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